

This dataset was prepared for the participants in the second championship phase of the Open challenge organized by the CHAIMELEON project for the training of AI models to answer a specific clinical question to improve diagnostic efficacy in rectal cancer patients. The main objective was, therefore, to **predict Extramural Vascular Invasion (EVI) and Mesorectal Fascia Invasion (MFI) in MRI**.

All 347 rectum cases (images and clinical data) collected until November 2023 were initially taken. Then 12 cases were excluded due to missing baseline MRI and other 4 cases due to missing axial and sagittal MRI series.

From the 331 resulting cases, 231 were selected for the training partition and so included in this dataset:

- **71 with EVI, 159 with no EVI**
- **55 with MFI, 176 with no MFI**

The original series (DICOM) with transversal and sagittal T2w images were selected, and an extra series was added with harmonized images in NIfTI format.

Only the imaging exam at diagnosis was included.

In the Open Challenge only demographic and diagnosis information (excl. imaging report and biopsy-related information) was shared with the participants to avoid introducing biases during model training. However, in this dataset, the complete clinical data is included in the eforms.json file to allow researchers further experimentation on different clinical endpoints.

The ground truth used during the Open Challenge can be found in the following variables:

- mesorectal_invasion_mr
- extramural_invasion_mr

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Contact info.: <https://chaimoleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 231

Subjects count: 231

Age range: Between 29 years and 89 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): RECTUM, ABDOMEN, PELVIS, Unknown

Modality: MR, Unknown